

Bengali Translation and Validation of Academic Resilience Scale in Bangladeshi School-Going Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to translate and validate the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) for use among Bangladeshi school students in Bengali. The ARS, developed by Martin and Marsh, measures students' ability to cope with academic challenges. This study addresses the gap in validated Bengali instruments for assessing academic resilience. A cross-sectional design study involving 234 students aged 12-18 years from two schools in Dhaka, Bangladesh, was used. The ARS underwent a rigorous translation process, which included two forward translations, two back translations, and comparisons of the original and translated versions. The data collected were collected by administering both the original and translated ARSs, with a one-week interval between administrations. Analysis was conducted using SPSS 29.0, employing descriptive statistics, Pearson correlations, Cronbach's alpha, and independent sample t-tests. Descriptive statistics revealed mean scores for the original ARS ($M = 23.78$, $SD = 7.456$) and the translated ARS ($M = 23.77$, $SD = 7.516$), indicating similar levels of academic resilience. Pearson correlations between the original and translated items ranged from .909 to .941 ($p < .01$). Cronbach's alpha was 0.747 for the original scale and 0.754 for the translated ARS, demonstrating acceptable reliability. No significant sex differences in resilience scores were found for either version. The Bengali-translated ARS is a reliable and valid tool for measuring academic resilience among Bangladeshi students. This validated scale offers a valuable resource for future research and interventions aimed at improving academic resilience. Future studies should address limitations and explore resilience factors in diverse contexts.

Keywords: *Academic Resilience, Bengali Translation, Scale Validation, School-going Students.*

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Introduction

Academic resilience, or the capacity to overcome adversity and persevere successfully in the academic context is a relevant dimension of student success (A. J. Martin & Marsh, 2006). Ultimately, resilient students are able to respond positively to adversity and perform well academically under adverse circumstances (Cassidy, 2016). It is a critical concept in educational psychology because it speaks directly to the well-being and performance success of students (Shahidi Delshad et al., 2023). While the literature on academic resilience is replete with theoretical discourse globally, there is a substantial dearth of relevantly validated tools for measuring academic resilience among school going Bengali students in Bangladesh.

One such instrument, the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) developed by Martin and Marsh (2006), is popularly used to measure academic resilience (A. J. Martin & Marsh, 2006). Academic resilience involves the dimensions of confidence, motivation and persistence. There is no available validated Bengali version

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of this scale, which limits its utility for young Bangladeshi students. Without such tools, it is difficult to perform rigorous research on academic resilience in this population and thereby develop targeted interventions that could improve outcomes for students.

The unique sociocultural context and educational challenges in Bangladesh necessitate the creation of a valid Bangla version for young school children. Furthermore, the academic structure in Bangladesh includes larger classrooms, inadequate resources and high-stakes examinations all of which can place added stress on young students (Kibria & Anwarul Abedin, 2022). Sociocultural factors are also significant for students' academic experience and resiliency (Alva, 1991). Thus, a culturally appropriate instrument is needed to measure academic resilience in this group.

The process of translating and validating a psychological scale must be rigorous so that the assessment is linguistically accurate and culturally relevant to the target population. This process involved forward and backward translation according to Pan & Puente (2012), expert review, and panel assessment, before pilot testing was conducted for the translated version to be above average (Pan & Puente, 2012). All these steps are essential for ensuring the stability of construct validity and reliability if the scale is adapted for different contexts. The adaptation of the Academic Resilience Scale to Bengali will enable its application in educational research and practices, which will ultimately lead to an overview of resilience level among Bangladeshi students.

The importance of academic resilience in promoting student well-being and academic success is well-documented. Studies have consistently demonstrated that resilient students are able to cope with academic stressors, retain high levels of motivation and demonstrate greater success in their educational pursuits (Chisholm-Burns et al., 2019; A. Martin, 2002). Another example is the research of Cassidy et al. In this vein, recent findings among pharmacy students showed academic resilience to be a protective factor for well-being as it was positively related to the stress deriving from academics (Cassidy et al., 2023). Similarly, a cross-sectional study by Amoadu et al. (Amoadu et al., 2024).

Additionally, academic resilience is reportedly linked to different underlying psychological factors, such as emotional intelligence and self-compassion that support better student wellness (Ononye et al., 2022; Rudd et al., 2021, 2023; Shahidi Delshad et al., 2023; Shen et al., 2024). Understanding of the relationships between empathy, perspective control and connectedness and academic resilience can be used to design comprehensive support programs for students. For instance, interventions structured to increase EI (emotional intelligence) or self-compassion may also work on developing AR, with positive results later in terms of academic success (Shahidi Delshad et al., 2023).

However, empirical research on academic resilience within the Bangladeshi context is scarce despite being pivotal for student accomplishment. Earlier work on resilience in Bangladesh focused broadly on the rubrics of higher education and COVID-19 (Kibria & Anwarul Abedin, 2022). Very little is known about academic resilience and this topic has not been explored as an area of risk among students attending schools who are facing their own specific challenges and stressors. A validated Bengali version of the Academic Resilience Scale can be a vital step in bridging this gap and helping identify factors that propagate or challenge academic success in this population which was found in previous studies in various contexts (Amoadu et al, 2024; Fatima et al, 2022; Shahidi et al, 2023).

The validation of the ARS in multiple cultural contexts has shown its strength and flexibility (Amoadu et al., 2024; Cassidy, 2016; Chisholm-Burns et al., 2019; Cui et al., 2023; Elnaem et al., 2024; Fatima et al., 2022; Rachmawati et al., 2021; Rudd et al., 2023; Surzykiewicz et al., 2019). For example, the scale was validated by Rachmawati et al. among social science students in Indonesia (Rachmawati et al., 2021). In a related study of collective culture, the same scale was adapted and validated by Cui et al. (Cui et al., 2023). These sources emphasize the universal application of the scale and the pivotal role of adaptation in the context of culture to guarantee accuracy and relevance. Therefore, validating the Urdu translation by Fatima et al. in Pakistan has also drawn attention to language and cultural considerations during adaptation (Fatima et al., 2022).

Apart from cultural adaptation, maintaining the original psychometric properties of the translated scale is also important. This approach helps us examine the scale which we developed for its reliability and validity through tests such as factor analysis, and correlation studies (Surzykiewicz et al., 2019). These steps are followed so that the translated scale correctly measures academic resilience and is suitable for effective use in studies. This stringent validation process also arises from pilot testing the measure in a sample that is characteristic of the model population to note any items not performing well and if necessary, to make corrections (Pan & Puente, 2012).

The translation and validation of the Academic Resilience Scale into Bangla offers insight for academics working in Bangladesh, and improves the understanding of academic resilience among school-going students. The study component reported in this article addresses a critical gap by offering such an instrument within the cultural and language context of these survivors. This information will help educators and policymakers develop interventions targeting the academic resilience of students who can thereby better overcome obstacles to educational success. The validated scale will then enable cross-cultural comparison work and a more comprehensive examination of how academic resilience influences student outcomes worldwide.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional research design to translate and validate the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) for Bengali-speaking school-going students in Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Study Population

The study population comprised 234 school students (111 males, 123 females) aged 12-18 years from two high schools, the Hazrat Shah Ali Model High School and the Oxford Pre-Cadet High School located in Dhaka, the capital city of Bangladesh. These schools were selected to ensure a representative sample of students from diverse backgrounds schools was the case for the students from different socioeconomic status studies. Participants of the required age, currently enrolled in participating schools, and who provided written informed consent were included in the study. Participants with significant cognitive impairment that affected their ability to participate in the study or those who were unwilling or unable to provide informed consent were excluded to maintain ethical standards and ensure the reliability of the results.

Measures

Demographic Information

Age and sex were recorded for each participant to provide demographic context (see Table 1).

Academic Resilience Scale (ARS)

The Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) developed by Martin and Marsh (2006) was used in this study (A. J. Martin & Marsh, 2006). The ARS is a six-item instrument designed to measure students' ability to effectively manage challenges, failures, and pressures in their academic lives. The scale uses a 7-point Likert format ranging from "not at all true of me" to "extremely true of me". The original ARS demonstrated strong reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89, indicating high internal consistency.

Translation Process

The translation and validation process for the Bengali version of the ARS adhered to established protocols to ensure both linguistic and cultural appropriateness:

Forward Translation

The ARS was translated from English to Bengali by two independent bilingual experts from psychology and public health backgrounds. This initial translation aimed to retain the semantic and conceptual integrity of the original scale.

Backward Translation

Subsequently, two different bilingual experts from psychology and public health backgrounds translated the Bengali version back into English. This step was designed to identify any discrepancies between the translated and original versions.

Comparison of Versions

The back-translated English versions were compared with the original English versions to evaluate the accuracy of the Bengali translation. This comparison involved aligning the translated Bengali version with the original and reverse English versions to assess the empirical equivalence and overall quality of the translation.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection was conducted in two phases:

Phase One

The translated Bengali version of the ARS was administered to the participants. The initial data collection was carried out in a classroom setting under controlled conditions to minimize external influences and ensure consistency on July 21, 2024.

Phase Two

One week after the initial data collection, the same participants were asked to complete the original English version of the ARS. This approach enabled a comparative analysis of the responses of the translated and original versions, providing insights into the reliability and validity of the Bengali translation on July 27, 2024.

Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study was performed using SPSS version 29.0 software. Descriptive statistics were first calculated to summarize sample demographics and overall scores on the original and translated Academic Resilience Scale (ARS). Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the relationship between items in the original and translated versions, providing information about the consistency of responses across both scales. Cronbach's alpha was determined for each version to assess the internal consistency and reliability of the ARS, with higher values indicating greater reliability. Additionally, independent sample t tests were conducted to explore potential sex differences in academic resilience scores for the original and translated versions, to reveal any significant differences according to sex.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in compliance with ethical standards and received approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at the Bangladesh Institute of Innovative Health Research (IRB Protocol Number: BIIHR-2024-004). Adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki was ensured throughout the research process. Permissions were obtained from the participating schools, and informed consent was secured from both the students and their guardians. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any adverse consequences.

Results

The results of this study provide a comprehensive evaluation of the translated Bengali version of the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) and its comparison with the original English version. The analysis included descriptive statistics, reliability assessments, and the examination of gender differences in academic resilience.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics and Mean ARS Scores of the Participants (n=234)

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentages	Original ARS Mean (\pm SD) Score	Translated ARS Mean (\pm SD) Score
Age	12-14 years	124	53	23.76 (\pm .669)	23.77 (\pm .674)
	15-16 years	96	41	23.79 (\pm .767)	23.76 (\pm .773)
	17-18 years	14	6	23.86 (\pm 2.059)	23.85 (\pm 2.088)
Sex	Male	111	47.4	23.52 (\pm .699)	23.58 (\pm .707)
	Female	123	52.6	24.01 (\pm .681)	23.94 (\pm .686)
Socioeconomic Status	Higher Class	34	14.5	23.75 (\pm .665)	23.78 (\pm .671)
	Middle Class	148	63.3	23.79 (\pm .723)	23.81 (\pm .731)
	Lower Class	52	22.2	23.65 (\pm .672)	23.73 (\pm .681)

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the 234 participants, 53% were aged 12-14 years, 41% were aged 15-16 years, and 6% were aged 17-18 years. The gender distribution was fairly balanced, with 47.4% male and 52.6% female students, mostly from middle class backgrounds (63.3%) (Table 1).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for the Original and Translated ARS Scores

Scale	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Original ARS scores	23.78	7.456	11	35
Translated ARS scores	23.77	7.516	9	36

Table 2 provides the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum scores for both the original and translated ARS items. The mean score (\pm SD) for the original ARS was 23.78 (\pm 7.456), indicating that, on average, participants reported moderate levels of academic resilience. The mean score for the translated ARS was 23.77 (\pm 7.516), suggesting comparable levels of resilience as measured by the translated scale (Table 2).

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics for Individual ARSs Items (Translated Version)

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Item 1	3.97	2.006	1	7
Item 2	3.97	2.008	1	7
Item 3	3.97	2.006	1	7
Item 4	3.93	1.547	1	7
Item 5	3.99	1.998	1	7
Item 6	3.93	1.594	1	7

Table 3 details the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum scores for each item on the translated ARS. The scores revealed that Item 1, Item 2, Item 3 and Item 5 received slightly higher average ratings than did the other items (Table 3).

Table 4. Pearson Correlation between the Original and Translated ARS Scores

Item	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p value
Item 1	.929	<.01
Item 2	.927	<.01
Item 3	.929	<.01
Item 4	.941	<.01
Item 5	.909	<.01
Item 6	.941	<.01

Pearson correlation was measured between the items on the original and translated ARSs (Table 4). Table 4 shows that the correlation coefficients ranged from .909 to .941, and were significant at the $p < .01$ level.

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha for the Original and Translated ARSs

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha
Original ARS	.747
Translated ARS	.754

The internal consistency of the original ARS and the translated ARS was measured by Cronbach's alpha (Table 5). Table 5 demonstrates that the Cronbach's alpha for the original ARS was 0.747, indicating acceptable reliability. The translated ARS demonstrated a similar level of reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.754.

Table 6. Independent Sample t Test for Sex Differences in ARS Scores

Scale	Gender	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p-value
Original ARS	Male	23.52	7.369	-.497	232	.620
	Female	24.01	7.557			
Translated ARS	Male	23.58	7.446	-.372	232	.710
	Female	23.94	7.604			

Independent sample t tests was used to reveal if there is any significant difference in the original ARS score and translated ARS according to sex (Table 6). Table 6 illustrates that there was no significant sex difference original ARS ($t = -.497$, $df = 232$, $p = .620$) or translated ARS ($t = -.372$, $df = 232$, $p = .710$).

Discussion

This study aimed to translate and validate the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) for secondary school students in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The main objectives were to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the translation and to compare its psychometric properties with those of the original English version. To achieve these objectives, this study makes a significant contribution to the literature on academic resilience, by providing a validated instrument for assessing resilience in a new linguistic and cultural context.

The importance of this study lies in its contribution to the field of educational psychology by providing a reliable and valid tool for assessing academic resilience in a new linguistic and cultural context. By translating and validating the ARS into Bengali, this research enables broader application of the scale, allowing educators and researchers to better understand and support the resilience of students in Bangladesh. This work aligns with previous studies that have emphasized the need for culturally and linguistically appropriate assessment tools (Cassidy, 2016; Cassidy et al., 2023; Cui et al., 2023; Fatima et al., 2022).

The results of the study demonstrated that the psychometric properties of the translated Bengali version of the ARS are comparable to those of the original English version. Specifically, the internal consistency of the translated ARS, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, was found to be similar to that of the original scale. Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficients between the items on the original and translated ARS were strong and significant, indicating that the translated version maintains the integrity of the original scale.

These findings are consistent with those of Martin and Marsh, who developed the ARS and established its validity and reliability in different educational settings (A. J. Martin & Marsh, 2006). The high correlation coefficients observed in this study are comparable to those reported by Shen, Feng, and Li in their concept analysis of academic resilience in nursing students (Shen et al., 2024). Similarly, the reliability of the translated ARS, as indicated by Cronbach's alpha, is in line with the findings of Fatima et al. and Chisholm-Burns et al., who reported robust reliability for their academic resilience instrument among pharmacy students (Chisholm-Burns et al., 2019; Fatima et al., 2022).

The lack of significant sex differences in academic resilience scores observed in this study is consistent with the findings of some related studies (Ononye et al., 2022; Shahidi Delshad et al., 2023), but contrasts with the findings of other studies that reporting sex gender differences in resilience (Amodu et al., 2024). The lack of significant gender differences may be explained by the fact that the educational environments and social expectations of students of both genders in the studied schools were similar. In addition, the balanced sex distribution in the sample may have contributed to the nonsignificant differences. Previous research, such as that of Gabrielli et al., highlights that academic resilience can be influenced by many factors, including cultural, family, and individual differences, which may explain the trends observed in this study (Gabrielli et al., 2022).

Limitations

Limitations of the study include potential biases related to the regional and socioeconomic characteristics of the sample. Participants came from two schools in Dhaka, which may not be fully representative of the diversity of educational contexts in Bangladesh. This geographic concentration may limit the ability to generalize the results to other regions with different educational and cultural contexts. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias, affecting the accuracy of the resilience measures.

Recommendations

Future research could extend this study by including a more diverse sample from different regions of Bangladesh to improve the generalizability of the results. Studying the impact of different educational contexts, such as rural or urban schools, on academic resilience would also be useful. Longitudinal studies could further explore how academic resilience develops over time and how it correlates with academic achievement and psychological well-being.

Moreover, exploring the relationship between academic resilience and other psychological constructs, such as emotional intelligence and self-compassion could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to academic success (Ononye et al., 2022; Shahidi Delshad et al., 2023). Integrating qualitative methods to capture students' personal experiences and perceptions of resilience could offer deeper insights into the contextual factors influencing academic resilience.

Conclusion

This study successfully translated and validated the Academic Resilience Scale (ARS) into Bengali, thereby contributing significantly to the assessment of academic resilience among Bangladeshi school-going students. The results confirmed that the translation of the ARS into Bengali retained the psychometric properties of the original English version, demonstrating high internal consistency and strong correlations with the original scale. This validation ensures that the translated instrument is a reliable

measure of academic resilience in the Bangladeshi context, thereby filling an important gap in the literature. The results showed that the original and translated ARSs yielded similar scores, indicating that the translated scale effectively captures the concept of academic resilience as the original scale did. Furthermore, the lack of significant gender differences in resilience scores is consistent with the findings of some existing research, but highlights the need to further explore resilience in different educational and demographic contexts. Despite its strengths, this study has several limitations, including its limited geographic scope and reliance on self-reported data, which may affect the generalizability and validity of its results. Future research should aim to include a more diverse sample and investigate other factors that influence academic resilience. Overall, the Bengali-translated ARS provides a valuable tool for researchers and educators in Bangladesh to assess and support school resilience. This study lays the foundation for additional research and interventions to enhance students' ability to meet learning challenges and succeed academically.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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